

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART XVII. THIOINDIGOID DYES DERIVED FROM DIPHENYL ETHER DISULPHONIC ACID

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4 : 5-4' : 5'-Diphenyl-*bis*-(3''-hydroxy-1''-thiophene)-ether' (I), prepared from diphenyl ether-4 : 4'-disulphonic acid, has been condensed with various *o*-diketones, and the corresponding *bis*-thioindigoid dyes have been obtained with a view to studying colour and its relation to chemical constitution

After having unsuccessful attempts to prepare dithioindigoid dyes from diphenyl-4 : 4'-disulphonic acid (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 339) and naphthalene-2:7-disulphonic acid (*ibid.*, 1955, 32, 423), it has been possible to prepare such dyes from diphenyl-methane-4 : 4'-disulphonic acid (*ibid.*, 1955, 32, 497). These dyes, although dithioindigoids and as such expected to be of much deeper in colour, have not been found so deep. The deficiency in depth of colour has been ascribed to the presence of the insulating group $-\text{CH}_2-$ in between the two thioindigoid chromophores, thus breaking the conjugated system of the whole molecule^c in two parts, producing the colour effect by only the duplication or addition of the two monothioindigoid parts on either side. The present investigation is an attempt to study further such dithioindigoid dyes with respect to their colour and chemical constitution, and it deals with dyes derived from diphenyl ether disulphonic acid so that in place of the methylene bridge therein, an ether linkage (-O-) is present in the present series.

As the ether linkage in these compounds should also act as an insulator, like the methylene group, breaking the conjugated system into fragments, something very different from the previous observation was not expected. This assumption has been realised on comparing the colour of these two series of dyes, excepting that the divalent oxygen appears to have a slightly greater chromophoric effect than the methylene group, as the dyes described herein have a slightly deeper shade.

For preparing these dyes, diphenyl ether has been converted successively into its disulphonic acid (*Annalen*, 1863, 126, 329; 1871, 159, 204), disulphochloride, dimercaptan, dithioglycolic acid and the latter cyclised to dithioindoxyl. This dithioindoxyl has been condensed with various *o*-diketones, and thus *bis*-thioindigoid dyes have been obtained.

The positions of the sulphonic acid groups in the diphenyl ether disulphonic acid having been known (Suter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1115), the structures of the dithioindoxyl (I) and the thioindigoid dyes (II), obtained from it, may be represented by the following formulae :

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Diphenyl ether-4:4'-disulphochloride was prepared by heating a mixture of diphenyl ether potassium disulphonate (35 g.) and PCl_5 (50 g.) on a water-bath for 2 hours when a semi-fluid mass was obtained. This was decomposed by ice and left overnight. The residue, after washing and drying, was crystallised from chloroform in small cubes, m.p. 131° . (Found: C, 39.12; H, 2.23. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{S}_2$ requires C, 39.23; H, 2.18 per cent).

Diphenyl Ether-4:4'-dimercaptan.—The above disulphochloride (whole quantity) was reduced with tin and HCl for 12 hours when a soft yellowish mass was obtained. This was filtered, washed first with HCl (conc.) and then with water. The residue was then extracted with benzene, the extract dried with calcium chloride, filtered and the benzene distilled off. The mercaptan, separating as shining yellow flakes, was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. $103-104^\circ$, yield 15 g. (Found: C, 61.47; H, 4.31. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{OS}_2$ requires C, 61.53; H, 4.27 per cent).

Diphenyl Ether-4:4'-dithioglycollic Acid.—The dimercaptan (4.8 g.) was dissolved in dilute caustic soda and to this monochloroacetic acid (4 g.), previously neutralised with caustic soda, was added. The mixture was warmed on a water-bath for an hour, filtered and the filtrate acidified with HCl . The dithioglycollic acid separating as a white voluminous precipitate was crystallised from dilute alcohol as white shining flakes, m.p. 164° , yield 6.2 g. (Found: C, 55.3; H, 3.9. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ requires C, 54.85; H, 4.0 per cent).

4:5:4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-(3"-hydroxy-1"-thiophene)-ether was prepared in the same way as *4:5:4':5'-diphenyl-bis-(3"-hydroxy-1"-thiophene)-methane* (*loc. cit.*) from the above diphenyl ether-dithioglycollic acid. The crude dithioindoxyl like the other similar compounds could not be purified on account of its susceptibility to oxidation, and so its acetic acid solution was used for condensation with various *o*-diketones. The thioindoxyl dissolves in dilute caustic soda with a greenish colour, but does not yield any precipitate of the *bis*-compound with potassium ferricyanide.

4:5:4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiopheno-ether-3:3-bis-indoi-indigo (IIa) was prepared by mixing the separate solutions of isatin and the above thioindoxyl in acetic acid and boiling the mixture for half an hour with the addition of HCl (conc., 0.5 c.c.). The violet-red precipitate obtained was filtered hot, washed with acetic acid and alcohol and crystallised from nitrobenzene as a violet-red crystalline mass, m.p. above 300° . It dissolves in alkaline hydrosulphite with a yellow colour and dyes cotton in pinkish violet shade. In H_2SO_4 (conc.) it dissolves with a greenish brown colour. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 3.3. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires C, 67.13; H, 2.8 per cent).

4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiopheno-ether-2:2-bis-acenaphthylene-indigo (IIb) was prepared, as described above, from acenaphthenequinone and dithioindoxyl and crystallised from nitrobenzene as tiny, pink needles, m.p. above 300°. It is not much soluble in alkaline hydrosulphite and dyes cotton in pink shade. It dissolves in H₂SO₄ (conc.) with a green colour. (Found: C, 74.32; H, 3.3. C₄₀H₁₈O₅S₂ requires C, 74.76; H, 2.8 per cent).

4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiopheno-ether-9:9-bis-phenanthrene-indigo (IIc) was prepared, as already described, from phenanthrenequinone and dithioindoxyl and obtained as a dark chocolate crystalline mass from nitrobenzene, m.p. above 300°. It dissolves in H₂SO₄ (conc.) with a brown colour and dyes cotton from alkaline hydrosulphite in chocolate-brown shade. (Found: C, 75.97; H, 3.25. C₄₄H₂₂O₅S₂ requires C, 76.68; H, 3.17 per cent).

4:5-4':5'-Diphenyl-bis-thiopheno-ether-1:1-bis-aceanthrylene-indigo (IIId) was prepared from aceanthraquinone and dithioindoxyl in acetic acid solution, as described above, and crystallised from nitrobenzene as a brownish violet crystalline mass, m.p. above 300°. It dyes cotton from hydrosulphite vat in copper-red shade and dissolves in H₂SO₄ (conc.) with a light green colour. (Found: C, 77.51; H, 3.02. C₄₈H₂₂O₅S₂ requires C, 77.62; H, 2.96 per cent).